

Response of Sweet Corn (*Zea mays* L. *Saccharata*) to RDN Applied through Various Organics

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Abstract

N is one of the most important factors in crop productivity. A field trial with variety Sugar-75 was carried out during rabi season, 2018 at Organic farm, NAU, Navsari, Gujarat, India, consisting 8 treatments and 4 replications in RBD to investigate the growth and yield response of sweet corn to N. The growth parameters fluctuated significantly due to different treatments and T5 (100 % RDN by CC) recorded significantly higher plant height at 30 (22.1 cm) and 60 (136.0 cm) DAS, while, at harvest, T7 (50% RDN by BC + 50% RDN by CC) noted greater plant height (146.1 cm) and was at par with all organic treatments. The treatment T5 also recorded significantly high dry matter accumulation up to 45 DAS though, at final growth stages, T7 produced significant amount of dry matter (46.96, 98.18 and 144.87 g plant⁻¹ at 60, 75 DAS and at harvest, respectively). At harvest, the yield parameters viz. number of cobs plant⁻¹ (1.27), cob length (26.22 cm) and cob weight (238.2 g) along with fresh cobs (26.07 t ha⁻¹), stover (8.0 t ha⁻¹) and total biomass yield (11.7 t ha⁻¹) also recorded considerably higher in T7 but, was statistically at par with CC integrated treatments (T6 and T8) in most cases. The increase in fresh cobs, stover and total biomass yields in T7 over T1 were 58.6, 70.2 and 58.1 %, respectively. The outcome, shows that N availability is the most limiting factor and require additional strategies to improve its efficacy under organic farming.

Keywords: Growth, RDN, organics, sweet corn, yield.

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Introduction

Green revolution has enhanced crop production through immense application of synthetic agro-chemicals with adopting nutrient-responsive, high-yielding varieties but, this production system is challenged via hindering productivity owing to its hostile effects on soil, environment, consumer and producer health. Increasing consciousness about environmental protection, agrochemicals and health risks are main causes of growing interest of alternate farming system. Customers are seeking for hazard

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free safe organic food throughout the world (Bardhan and Patel, 2016). The demand for organic food is globally increasing with average annual growth of 20- 25%, with commercial production of certified organic products in more than 130 countries, nowadays (Ramesha et al., 2017).

As organic farming system avoids synthetic inputs application and depend upon biologically supplied nutrient, plant protection and animal manures, crop residues, crop rotations along with mineral grade rock additives. These approaches are combined for attaining quality crop products without harming environment, society and farm labour as organic farming works in coordination with nature (Meena et al., 2013; Alexandra, 2013).

Organic agriculture could be innovative effort for sustainability. The key barriers against this system are: will food production through this system be adequate for population? will this system meet the entire nutrient provisions?

Though, organic system enhances soils fertility mainly N accessibility which is most limiting factor of crop productivity owing to its problematic management in organic farming (Mikkelsen and Hartz, 2008). N is essential nutrient of farm productivity and its annual application rate in agriculture (about 67.84 million tons) indicates widespread significance of N (Chen et al., 2014).

Organic system relies on on-farm organic inputs to supply enough N however, synchronization of N liberation with the plant request from organics is most problematic. As N release is crucial for N availability in organic farming, several internal and external factors fluctuates mineral N liberation to a great extent (Brady and Weil, 2010). Thus, to increase productivity of the organic farming, understanding the dynamics of N along with affecting factors are decisive. Many factors collectively affect the nutrient release of organics and their availability to crop viz, organics' quality (C/N ratio, composition, properties), environmental and soil conditions (soil properties, temperature, moisture content etc.) as well as management practices hence, should be considered in soil fertility management, particularly in organic farming (Xiaomin et al., 2017).

Organics release organic and other microbial products during decomposition, enhance the availability of native nutrients by providing supplementary plant nutrients (Stevenson, 1982). Furthermore, almost all non-legumes absorb NH_4^+ (ammonium) and/or NO_3^- (nitrate) N from soil. Many plant species also utilize simple compound of organic N though, did not consider as a major plant nutrition basis as fertilizer-responsive hybrid varieties for modern farming are being employed in organic farming (Murphy et al., 2007 and Maggio et al., 2008).

N scarcity limits crop production as a vital part of many essential compounds viz, chlorophyll, porphyrins, enzymes, hormones, proteins, amino acids, nucleic acids, nucleotides, alkaloids, vitamins etc. thus, its management in organic agriculture is crucial for optimum plant growth and productivity. High N may disturb crop growth, development, quality and environment (Mikkelsen and Hartz, 2008) so, supplementary efforts required to manage N in organic agriculture.

N availability is pivotal factor in improving crop productivity. So, it is crucial to develop appropriate management methods apt to synchronize nutrient accessibility with crop demand throughout growing season. As organics partially decompose in a single season (Havlin et al., 2014) hence, to develop a sustainable crop productivity and soil fertility system, understanding the mineralization pattern of types and amount of applied organics is crucial, consequently, long-term platform of repeated organics supply is essential to enhance soil organic N and N mineralization (Gaskell et al., 2006).

Conventional farming trusts upon chemicals, while organic system relies on soil organic matter management for improving crop productivity. Soil fertility is a main aspect of productivity in all agricultural systems and N is a key factor of productivity restriction in organic system so, plant residues addition is a crucial method of improved soil fertility in a sustainable manner.

In view of these facts, this experiment was laid out to examine the response of sweet corn to application of RDN through different organics during growing season and at harvest.

Corn maize (*Zea mays* L.) is annual cereal crop grows under variety of soil and climatic conditions. It is most important staple food crop in India accounting for about 10% of total cereal production after the wheat and rice (Anon., 2018). In India, maize is cultivated on 8.49 million hectares with current production of 26.0 million tonnes and average productivity of 2.54 t ha⁻¹ (Anon., 2018). In Gujarat, maize is cultivated across the Northern to Southern districts and sweet corn cultivation is increasing with consumers and agro-based industries demand in Gujarat.

Sweet corn (*Zea mays* L. *Saccharata*) is a hybrid variety of maize (*Zea mays* L.) specially raised to increase sugar content containing about 20.0 % sugar compared to 3.0 % sugar in dent corn (Bhupender et al, 2012). The fruit of sweet corn plant is the corn kernel. The green cobs are eaten, roasted or boiled. It is good source of energy, protein, A, C and B6, thiamine, riboflavin, niacin as major vitamins and is relatively high in oil content (linolenic and oleic acids) with worthy amount of Ca, P, Fe and K.

The demand for healthy and nutritional product is main forces of cumulative consumption of sweet corn. Thus, organic sweet corn has great potential of providing better revenue to growers, employment for poor rural as well as raw material to Agro based pharmacological industries. The unfamiliarity with commercial and dietary importance of sweet corn along with low productivity owing to scarcity of suitable production skills are key limitations for its popularization among growers and consumers.

As, sweet corn requires fertile soils for optimum production whereas, N is key factor for improving productivity and poorly available in organic farming. Therefore, development of suitable nutrient management tactics capable of synchronizing nutrient availability with crop demand during growing period is essential. Understanding the nutrient release pattern of types and amount of applied organics should be priority in maintaining the sustainable soil fertility and crop productivity due to partial decomposition of organics in a single season. Considering these facts, the present study entitled “Response of sweet corn (*Zea mays* L. *Saccharata*) to RDN applied through various organics” was carried out with the objective of studying the effects of different organics application on growth, biomass and yield of sweet corn.

Materials and Methods

The field trial was laid out at Organic Farm, ASPEE College of Horticulture and Forestry, Navsari Agricultural University, Navsari (Gujarat state), India. Navsari is located at 20.95 °N latitude and 72.93 °E longitude in tropical region; having mean elevation of 10 meters above the sea level and falls in agro-ecological situation III (AES III) of South Gujarat Heavy Rainfall Zone-I, climatically characterized by moderately cold winter and fairly hot and humid summer, humid and warm monsoon with heavy rainfall (around 1500 mm). The soils of experimental area popularly known as “Deep Black” soils of South Gujarat characterized by heavy textured deep clayey, moderately drained with good water retentive capacity.

Different on farm organics viz. Farmyard Manure (FYM), Biocompost (BC), Vermicompost (VC) and Castor cake (CC) were used to supply the 100 % recommended dose of nitrogen (RDN) according to treatments. Before application of organics, they were homogenized thoroughly and representative sample from each organic taken for nutrients analysis and the mean values are represented in Table 1. In order to supply 100 % RDN to sweet corn (120 kg N ha⁻¹), the required quantity of different organics per gross plot was calculated based on N content of the source (Table 1). As per layout, the entire quantity of organics broadcasted uniformly in respective plot and subsequently, incorporated in soil with hand harrow before a week of seed sowing.

After harvest of previous crop, weeds and crop residues were removed from the experimental field, then deep ploughed by tractor drawn disc-plough and kept as fellow for a month. Before sowing, a shallow tillage was done again by using tractor drawn cultivator in both the directions followed by disc harrow and then levelled by cultivator cum plank tool on February 11, 2018. After land preparation, the experimental area was divided into four replications as per Randomized Block Design (RBD) and then, different treatments were randomly allocated in each replication. In order to supply 100 % RDN, different organic sources were used as 8 treatments viz, T1 (Control/no organics), T2 (100 % N through FYM), T3 (100 % N through biocompost), T4: (100 % N through vermicompost), T5 (100 % N through castor cake), T6 (50 % N through FYM + 50 % N through CC), T7 (50 % N through BC + 50 % N through CC), T8 (50 % N through VC + 50 % N through CC). Different organic manures were applied as per treatments and mixed thoroughly in soil with the help of hand harrow on February 12, 2018. The experiment was laid out in 2018, Rabi season with 32 experimental plots with grass area of 6.0m*4.0m and net area 4.8m*3.2m.

Healthy certified sweet corn seeds (*Zea mays* var. *Saccharata* L. Sturt), variety, Sugar-75 was obtained from Organic farm, ASPEE CHF, NAU, Navsari. As stated by recommended spacing, the seeds were sown in rows at 60cm*20cm spacing and 12.0 kg ha⁻¹ seed rate by dibbling method on February 19, 2018. Besides, two seeds were placed in each dibble at about 5.0 cm depth. At 15 DAS, thinning operation was carried out for maintaining uniform plant population and gap filling was not required owing to healthy germination.

First flood irrigation was applied immediately after sowing, the following were given at critical growth stages and supplementary irrigations relating to soil and climate conditions with total numbers of 8 irrigations during trial.

In order to keep the trial field free of weeds during growing season, three manual weeding operation (at 20, 35 and 50 DAS) was done by cono-weeder. Foliar application of neem oil @ 0.2% was carried out at 20 DAS to control cutworms and also the same dose was sprayed and at 45 DAS to control rarely reported shoot borer and as a preventive measure for any unpredictable diseases.

Table 1. Organics Quantity Applied in the Trial

Sr.	Treatment details	N content in organics (%)	Quantity required (t ha ⁻¹)
No	Tranche	Spread (basis point) (Gaussian copula)	Spread (basis point) (Student copulas)
1.	T ₁ :- Control (no organics)	-	-
2.	T ₂ :- FYM	0.82	14.6
3.	T ₃ :- Biocompost	1.72	7.0
4.	T ₄ :- Vermicompost	1.25	9.6
5.	T ₅ :- Castor cake	4.13	3.0
6.	T ₆ :- FYM + Castor cake	-	7.3 + 1.5
7.	T ₇ :- Biocompost + Castor cake	-	3.5 + 1.5
8.	T ₈ :- Vermicompost + Castor cake	-	4.8 + 1.5

In each plot, ten plants were randomly tagged and their height was measured at 30 and 60 DAS and at harvest in centimetre (cm) from base of the plant to the base of fully opened top leaf and the obtained values were averaged out. Net plots was divided in to two equal parts and dry matter accumulation was periodically measured at 15, 30, 45, 60 and 75 DAS from selected half net plot. In each period, plants were cut-off at the bottom from each plot in one meter raw and labelled, washed with DW, sun dried for 2 days and then oven dried at 65 ± 1oC till constant weight. The oven-dried samples immediately weighed

and the obtained average values were expressed in g plant⁻¹ and kg ha⁻¹. The cob and stover yields values of sweet corn were measured from remaining half of the net plot.

Fresh cobs harvested twice at optimum milking stage were weighed plot wise and total yield expressed as fresh cob yield in t ha⁻¹. while, stover was harvested on May 20, 2018, air dried in plot for a week then weighted and the obtained weight was converted into t ha⁻¹. In each net plot the total number of cobs were counted and obtained values were calculated as number of cobs plant⁻¹. Ten cobs were selected randomly, measured from the base to the tip, obtained values were averaged and expressed as cob length (cm). Digital Vernier Caliper was used to measure the diameter of the same cobs and values were converted in girth and shown as cob girth (cm). The same 10 cobs from each plot were oven dried at 65 ± 1 oC to constant weight and obtained values were used to calculate dry cob yield in t ha⁻¹.

Table 2. Plant Height of Sweet Corn as Affected by Different Organics

Treatments	Periodical plant height (cm)		
	30 DAS	60 DAS	At harvest
T ₁ :- Control	12.6	104.8	119.9
T ₂ :- 100% N by FYM	17.1	120.2	138.9
T ₃ :- 100% N by BC	17.1	131.5	140.5
T ₄ :- 100% N by VC	16.9	128.3	136.6
T ₅ :- 100% N by CC	22.1	136.0	138.3
T ₆ :- 50% N by FYM+50% N by CC	17.6	127.0	140.7
T ₇ :- 50% N by BC+50% N by CC	19.2	135.5	146.1
T ₈ :- 50% N by VC+50% N by CC	17.8	132.5	143.2
Mean	17.5	126.9	138.0
SEm (±)	0.82	5.80	4.48
CD at 5 %	2.41	17.06	13.18
CV (%)	9.36	9.14	6.49
Note: Recommended dose of N (100 % N), Farm Yard Manure (FYM), Biocompost (BC), Vermicompost (VC), Castor cake (CC)			

The recorded data were arranged in form of data analysis and the suggested standard statistical method of Panse and Sukhatme (1967) for RBD was adopted. Treatments comparison and ANOVA was computed according to the method and incorporated in results.

Results

Plant Height

The data regarding plant height at 30 and 60 DAS and at harvest in table 2 shown that all organic treatments recorded noticeably higher plant height over control (T₁) at all stages. At early and middle crop growth stages (30 DAS and 60 DAS), T₅ recorded significantly maximum plant height (22.1 cm and 136.0 cm, respectively)

over rest of treatments while, stayed analogous with all organic treatments at 60 DAS only. At harvest, T₇ (50 % RDN by BC + 50 % RDN by CC) noted significant plant height (146.1 cm) but, stayed statistically at par with rest of treatments except control.

Dry Matter Accumulation

Periodical dry matter productions also fluctuated considerably by different organics (Table 3). T₃ recorded significant amount of dry matter at early crop growth stages *i.e.* 0.23, 1.59 and 26.70 g plant⁻¹ at 15, 30 and 45 DAS, respectively but, stayed analogous with T₇ in all three intervals. At latter stages, T₇ was

superior in attaining high amount of dry matter *i.e.* 46.96, 98.18 and 144.87 g plant⁻¹ at 60, 75 DAS and at harvest, respectively but, remained at the same bar with T₈ at all the three observations, with T₅ at 60 DAS and T₆ at harvest.

Table 3. Periodical Dry Matter Production of Sweet Corn as Affected by Different Organic

Treatments	Dry matter production (g plant ⁻¹)					
	15 DAS	30 DAS	45 DAS	60 DAS	75 DAS	At Harvest
T ₁ :- Control	0.16	1.01	12.95	24.34	47.91	91.15
T ₂ :- 100% N by FYM	0.17	1.13	16.63	31.80	68.05	116.39
T ₃ :- 100 % N by BC	0.20	1.35	22.77	40.47	84.89	126.10
T ₄ :- 100% N by VC	0.18	1.30	20.59	36.06	78.90	121.27
T ₅ :- 100 % N by CC	0.23	1.59	26.70	44.52	78.61	117.25
T ₆ :- 50% N by FYM+50% N by CC	0.18	1.28	20.32	37.39	84.67	132.63
T ₇ :- 50% N by BC+50% N by CC	0.22	1.52	25.22	46.96	98.18	144.78
T ₈ :- 50% N by VC+50% N by CC	0.21	1.40	22.65	42.06	92.14	138.45
Mean	0.19	1.32	20.98	37.95	79.17	123.50
SEm (±)	0.01	0.05	1.02	1.97	3.91	5.62
CD at 5 %	0.03	0.16	3.00	5.81	11.49	16.53
CV (%)	11.14	8.28	9.74	10.41	9.88	9.10

Yield Attributes

The data regarding to yield attributes of sweet corn presented in table 4 indicated that yield attributes viz. number of cobs plant⁻¹, cob length (cm) and single cob weight (g) affected significantly due to different organics either through single or combined sources and recorded higher mean values over control (T₁) with an exception of cob girth (cm). Amongst organics treatments, T₇ recorded greater values of cob length (26.22 cm), single cob weight (238.2 g cob⁻¹) and number of cobs plant⁻¹ (1.27 cobs plant⁻¹) yet, was at par with all organic treatments in case of cob length, with T₆ and T₈ in case of number of cobs plant⁻¹ and with T₆ in case of single cob weight. Furthermore, cob girth did not differ considerably due to different organics.

Yields

The results of fresh cob yield and total biomass production (dry cob + stover) at harvest shown in table 5 revealed that yield components differed significantly due to different organics. Fresh cobs yield and biomass reported significantly higher with all the organic treatments over control (T₁). Treatment T₇ yielded higher fresh cobs (26.07 t ha⁻¹), dry cobs (3.69 t ha⁻¹), stover (8.0 t ha⁻¹) and total biomass (11.7 t ha⁻¹) while, stayed statistically analogous with T₆ and T₈ in all cases. The degree of upsurge in fresh cobs and stover yields as well as biomass in T₇ over T₁ were 58.6, 70.2 and 58.1 per cent, respectively.

Discussion

In the present field investigation, 100 % RDN was applied through varied on-farm different organics to know the performance of sweet corn variety, Sugar-75 under South Gujarat agro-climatic condition.

Table 4. Yield Attributes of Sweet Corn as Affected by Different Organics at Harvest

Treatments	Yield attributes			
	Number of cobs plant ⁻¹	Cob length (cm)	Single cob weight (g)	Cob girth (cm)
T ₁ :- Control	1.08	23.15	185.9	14.32
T ₂ :- 100% N by FYM	1.15	24.80	215.0	15.03

T₃ :- 100% N by BC	1.19	25.20	218.8	14.96
T₄ :- 100% N by VC	1.17	24.78	212.2	14.77
T₅ :- 100% N by CC	1.19	25.41	225.2	15.08
T₆ :- 50% N by FYM+50% N by CC	1.22	25.75	228.2	15.15
T₇ :- 50% N by BC+50% N by CC	1.27	26.22	238.2	15.70
T₈ :- 50% N by VC+50% N by CC	1.25	25.23	226.7	15.36
Mean	1.19	25.06	218.7	15.04
SEm (±)	0.024	0.53	3.58	0.28
CD at 5 %	0.07	1.55	10.54	NS
CV (%)	3.98	4.20	3.28	3.74

The recorded plant height was significantly higher (22.1 cm) at early stage (30 DAS) by application of 100 % RDN through CC (T₅) over the rest of treatments and the extent of increase in was 75.4 per cent over control (Table 2). Similarly, dry matter accumulation was also significantly higher in same treatment (T₅) up to 45 DAS with corresponding values of 0.23, 1.59 and 26.70 g plant⁻¹ at 15, 30 and 45 DAS, respectively (Table 3) however, remained at the same bar with T₇ in all cases. In this case, the magnitude of dry matter upsurge in T₅ over T₁ was 43.8, 57.4 and 106.2 %, respectively.

Though, after 45 DAS, the plant height was recorded significantly higher at 60 DAS (136.0 cm) in T₅ and at harvest (146.1 cm) in T₇ over control (T₁) however, they were at par with all organic treatments at both the stages (Table 3). The recorded dry matter production was also significantly higher at 60 (46.96 g plant⁻¹), 75 (98.18 g plant⁻¹) DAS and at harvest (144.87 g plant⁻¹) in treatment T₇ but, stayed analogous with T₅ and T₈ at 60 DAS, with T₈ at 75 DAS and with T₆ and T₈ at harvest (Table 3). The magnitude of dry matter accumulation upsurge in T₇ over T₁ at 60, 75 DAS and at harvest was 92.9, 104.9 and 58.8 %, respectively. It obvious that castor cake contained treatment (T₅) was considerably better at early growth stage, but failed to stay dominant at harvest of sweet corn.

Entirely, the trial land was appropriate for sweet corn except available N as it was below its availability criteria. Besides, the applied organics had diverse C/N ratio and nutritional values as well as varied mineralization rates. Former investigations also indicated the crop growth (Mirza et al., 2010 and Atiyeh et al., 2000) and mineralization rate (Abbasi et al., 2015) differs through different organics. Castor cake is a concentrated organic manure with rapid mineralization due to low C/N ratio amongst the organic applied in present experiment, thus, supplies more available N and uptake at early growth stage as proved by measuring plant growth in this investigation. Gupta et al. (2004), Vaughn et al. (2010), Elamin and Madhavi (2015), Ramesha et al. (2017) and Gomes et al. (2017) indicated that concentrated organics provides available N to the plant earlier than other organics due to low C/N ratio and rapid mineralization. Mirza et al. (2010), Yadav et al. (2013) and Nurhidayati et al. (2018) also stated that organics with low C/N ratio deliver balanced nutrition to plants and positively affect the plants growth. The application of castor cake might be possible reasons of augmented plant height and dry matter at early growth stage.

Table 5. Yields of Sweet Corn as Affected by Different Organics

Treatments	Yields of sweet corn (t ha ⁻¹)			
	Fresh cobs	Dry cobs	Stover	Total dry matter
T₁ :- Control	16.44	2.69	4.75	7.44
T₂ :- 100% N by FYM	20.52	3.04	6.55	9.58
T₃ :- 100% N by BC	22.32	3.26	7.01	10.28
T₄ :- 100% N by VC	20.66	3.03	6.76	9.79
T₅ :- 100% N by CC	21.85	3.28	6.28	9.56

T₆ - 50% N by FYM+50% N by CC	23.97	3.43	7.34	10.76
T₇ - 50% N by BC+50% N by CC	26.07	3.69	8.04	11.72
T₈ - 50% N by VC+50% N by CC	24.45	3.48	7.75	11.23
Mean	22.03	3.24	6.81	10.05
SEm (\pm)	1.02	0.17	0.35	0.42
CD at 5 %	3.00	0.50	1.02	1.23
CV (%)	9.28	10.68	10.19	8.29

Similarly, the number of cobs plant⁻¹, cob length and cob weight at harvest were also documented higher values i.e. 1.27, 26.22 cm and 238.2 g cob⁻¹, respectively by treatment T₇ (Table 4) but, stayed statistically parallel with T₆ and T₈ in number of cobs plant⁻¹, with all organic treatments in case of cob length and only with T₆ in case of cob weight. Although, highest cob girth (15.70 cm) was noted in same treatment (T₇), it failed to be significant due to different organics.

Significantly higher growth and yield attributes documented in treatment T₇ also mirrored in fresh cobs and biomass yields as higher fresh cobs (26.07 t ha⁻¹), stover (8.04 t ha⁻¹) and total biomass (11.72 t ha⁻¹) yields of sweet corn were recorded in T₇ and remained analogous with T₆ and T₈ as stated with yield attributes (Table 4). Moreover, the extent increase of fresh cobs 45.8, 58.6 and 48.7 %, stover 54.5, 69.3 and 63.2 % and total biomass yields was 44.6, 57.5 and 50.9 % over the control (T₁) in treatments T₆, T₇ and T₈, respectively.

Generally, supply of 100 % RDN by integrating 50 % through CC and residual 50 % either through BC (T₇), VC (T₈) or FYM (T₆) found pointedly superior in enhancing growth and yield ascribing features and accordingly, fresh cobs and stover yields of sweet corn in comparison to rest of treatments.

The observed difference in growth and yield attributes and accordingly, in fresh cobs and stover yields of sweet corn might be due to nutrient release potential of applied organics particularly N-mineralization and subsequently absorption by sweet corn. The outcomes of these debates indicates that at initial growth stage, the noticeable growth rate in castor cake supplied treatment (T₅) might be attributed to synchronization of N availability with plant demands at this stage however, was fruitless in employing noteworthy result toward the maturity stage. It could be attributed to scarcity of mineral N at grand growth stage as early mineralized N might diminished in root rhizosphere. Lima et al. (2011), Koari et al. (2014), Joshi et al. (2016) and Ramesha et al. (2017) also revealed that castor cake comprised treatments executed superior at initial growth stage yet, castor cake integrated with other organics yielded more biomass and fresh cobs of sweet corn. Norman et al. (2003), Mirza et al. (2010) and Atiyeh et al. (2000) also concluded that varied plant growth could be attributed to variation in nutrient sources and nutrients availability.

Over all, at harvest of sweet corn, considerably higher and statistically analogous values of yield and yield components were documented in CC integrated (T₆, T₇ and T₈) treatments at harvest. It might be attributed to synchronization of N requirements during growing period particularly at grand growth stage due to optimal C/N ratio. Kowaljow et al. (2010) and Yadav et al. (2013) also stated that supply of blended organics with low C/N ratio deliver balanced plant nutrition and positively affect the yield. The outcomes of current trail are analogous with earlier results of Zia et al. (1992), Mirza et al. (2010), Pande et al. (2015), Canatoy (2018) and Khuwaja et al. (2018) in diverse climates..

Conclusion

A field trial concluded that plant growth and yield attributes as well as cobs and stover yields of sweet corn varied considerably due to various organics. Plant height, dry matter accumulation, yield and yield attributes were significantly higher with all the organic treatments over control. In general, supplying 100

% RDN by blending 50 % through CC and remaining 50 % either through BC, VC or FYM considerably enhanced growth and yield related aspects and accordingly, fresh cobs and stover yields of sweet corn. According to overall trial outcomes, it can be stated that periodical soil and plant N content was low mainly at grand growth stage resulting in relatively low yields than modern farming systems of the region and proved that N is the most restrictive factor for the optimal productivity. Thus, necessitate further approaches for improved productivity under organic farm of the region. In conclusion, supply of RDN through organics synchronize nutrient availability thus, increase crop productivity, ensure healthy food products and improve soil health as well as fertility.

Conflict of Interests

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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